

Multi-agent Multi-contact Path Planning with HPP

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Abstract

This demonstration paper presents the first attempt using HPP, a new path planner, for multi-agent multi-contact path planning. More specifically, a few HyQ robots, loaded on a Boeing 747-400 airplane, need to move to the emergency exits. The trajectories were first generated, based on which the contact sequences were specified. Finally the motion was illustrated in animation. This work was also the first attempt introducing Agent-Oriented concepts to multi-contact path planning in HPP.

1 Introduction

HPP (Humanoid Path Planner) is a new open-source software designed for complex classes of motion planning problems, such as navigation among movable objects, manipulation and contact-rich locomotion [1]. It adopts a clear object oriented architecture and can be extended to path planning for other types of robots. Rbprm [2] is a module that extends HPP with a reachability-based algorithm that generates acyclic contacts from a specified trajectory. HPP was developed mostly to handle planning tasks for a single robot. This project aimed at exploring possible extension of HPP as a Multi-agent path planning system. More specifically, multiple HyQ robots [3] were to move to the emergency exits of a Boeing 747-400 airplane without collision with the airplane or each other. Our attempt followed a three-phase hierarchical approach: the trajectories were first generated, based on which, the contacts were specified. Then the motion was illustrated in animation.

2 Design and Implementation

2.1 Trajectory Planning

A simplified Boeing 747-400 was first initialised in HPP (Fig. 1-a). Following that agents were loaded with the initial and goal configuration specified (Fig. 1b and 1d). Before planning, each agent was asked to generate a default trajectory. They were then registered on the platform to whom they propose plans based on the location of other agents. Once the platform detects a collision (e.g. Fig. 1-c), the agents were asked to re-plan from then on. If the agent failed to generate a valid plan, its default plan was loaded. If there is a collision when all agents use their default plans, we backtrack to a validate previous moment.

2.2 Contact Planning

Based on the trajectory, sequences of acyclic contacts were generated using a reachability-based planner [2]. The contact configurations were then exported to a file in preparation for the animation.

Figure 1: Planning and collision avoidance of 4 HyQ robot avatars in a simplified Boeing airplane

2.3 Animation

After loading the contact configuration of each robot, the platform can demonstrate the locomotion by repeatedly refreshing the agents' configuration in display. Users may choose to have an external view or internal view.

2.4 Implementation and Evaluation

HPP follows a client-server based design pattern. A *client* consisted of a *robot*, a *problem* as well as some *obstacles*. At the trajectory planning stage, the agent class was inherited from the client class for better management of interaction with the platform and reasoning tasks. For every planning task, a new problem was defined and the obstacles were reloaded.

This project used the Python API of HPP. A complete 3-step planning procedure may take a few minutes. The project is available online ¹.

3 Conclusion and Acknowledgement

This project was a first attempt using HPP for the task of multi-agent path planning with contacts. The project unveiled possible changes of HPP for better management of multiple agents. The current HPP implementation cannot perform reasoning about multiple planning problems in parallel. Reuse of intermediate planning results are possible but not implemented. The project implemented a naive collision avoidance algorithm, which could be further optimised. The project was a part of Shuai Wang's internship supervised by Dr. Nicolas Mansard. Detailed help and guidance from Dr. Steve Tonneau and Mr. Joseph Mirabel were also much appreciated.

References

- [1] Joseph Mirabel, Steve Tonneau, Pierre Fernbach, Anna-Kaarina Seppälä, Mylène Campana, Nicolas Mansard, and Florent Lamiroux. Hpp: a new software for constrained motion planning. In *IEEE/RSJ Intelligent Robots and Systems*, October 2016.
- [2] Steve Tonneau, Nicolas Mansard, Chonhyon Park, Dinesh Manocha, Franck Multon, and Julien Pettré. A reachability-based planner for sequences of acyclic contacts in cluttered environments. In *International Symposium on Robotics Research*, 2015.
- [3] Barkan Ugurlu, Ioannis Havoutis, Claudio Semini, and Darwin G Caldwell. Dynamic trot-walking with the hydraulic quadruped robot hyq: Analytical trajectory generation and active compliance control. In *2013 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*, pages 6044–6051. IEEE, 2013.

¹The demonstration videos were embedded on the project page: <https://airobert.github.io/MMPP-BNAIC/>. The source code and instructions were also made available there.